

Extension of the Trotterized Unitary Coupled Cluster to Triple Excitations

Mohammad Haidar,^{†,‡,¶} Marko J. Rančić,[¶] Yvon Maday,^{‡,§} and Jean-Philip Piquemal^{*,†}

[†]*Sorbonne Université, Laboratoire de Chimie Théorique(UMR-7616-CNRS), 4 place Jussieu-75005 Paris, France*

[‡]*Sorbonne Université, CNRS, Université Paris Cité, Laboratoire Jacques Louis Lions (LJLL), 4 place Jussieu-75005 Paris, France*

[¶]*TotalEnergies, Tour Coupole La Défense, 2 Pl. Jean Millier, 92078 Paris, France*

^{*}*Institut Universitaire de France, Paris, France*

E-mail: Mohammadhaidar2016@outlook.com, jean-philip.piquemal@sorbonne-universite.fr

Abstract

The Trotterized Unitary Coupled Cluster Single and Double (UCCSD) ansatz has recently attracted interest due to its use in Variation Quantum Eigensolver (VQE) molecular simulations on quantum computers. However, when the size of molecules increases, UCCSD becomes less interesting as it cannot achieve sufficient accuracy. Including higher-order excitations is therefore mandatory to recover the UCC's missing correlation effects. In this Letter, we extend the Trotterized UCC approach via the addition of (true) Triple T excitations introducing UCCSDT. We also include both spin and orbital symmetries. Indeed, in practice, these later help to reduce unnecessarily circuit excitations and thus accelerate the optimization process enabling to tackle larger molecules. Our initial numerical tests (12-14 qubits) show that UCCSDT improves the overall accuracy by at least two-orders of magnitudes with respect to standard UCCSD. Over-

all, the UCCSDT ansatz is shown to reach chemical accuracy and to be competitive with the CCSD(T) gold-standard classical method of quantum chemistry.

Introduction

The use of quantum computers is a promising strategy to overcome challenges occurring in the area of quantum chemistry.¹⁻⁵ Such hardware potentially facilitate the encoding of the full configuration interaction (FCI) wavefunction of the many-electron molecular system thanks to entangled quantum bits or qubits. In classical computers, the FCI includes a number of determinants which scales exponentially with the number of electrons denoted n_e , as roughly $O(n_o^{n_e})$, where n_o is the number of spin-orbitals, which makes the manipulation and storage of the wavefunction inefficient.⁶⁻⁸ However, using a quantum computer, we can instead store the (FCI) wavefunction by using only n_o orbitals which corresponds to n_o qubits.¹ This potential quantum advantage has recently excited both hardware and software communities generating rapid progresses in the field. Several quantum algorithms have been developed, and among them, the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE)⁹⁻¹² appears well suited for its practical implementation on present Noisy Intermediate Scaled Quantum (NISQ) devices.^{13,14} VQE simulations have been performed numerically for molecules using various virtual noiseless simulators¹⁵⁻¹⁸ and have been tested experimentally on actual NISQ devices.^{9,19-22} An important component in VQE is the parametrized ansatz, which represents the trial wavefunction and is implemented as a quantum circuit, composed of unitary quantum gates, that measures the energy expectation value of the trial wavefunction and then its parameters are updated in a classical optimization loop. The Unitary Coupled-Cluster (UCC) ansatz was used when VQE was initially proposed, and has granted lots of attention since then. Indeed, UCC includes several attractive features: (i) it is chemistry-inspired since it is a unitary version of the classical coupled-cluster method, which is among the most accurate classical quantum chemistry methods for many-body simulation (see exhaustive recent reviews in^{23,24}); (ii) A variant of the UCC theory including single (S) and double (D) excitations called UCCSD is well suited for a direct

use on the current NISQ circuits (see comprehensive reviews of UCCSD in^{25,26}). Moreover, the Suzuki-Trotter approximation²⁷ allows separating out the ansatz into a product form of individual exponentials. This version of the ansatz is then denoted Trotterized UCC. Since it is unitary, it can be easily transformed into well-defined unitary gates and therefore its implementation is possible on NISQ devices.

The Trotterized UCCSD ansatz is well documented^{25,26,28–30} and has been successfully tested for small molecules.^{31–33} However, UCCSD exhibits a limited accuracy in strongly correlated systems similarly as the classical CCSD ansatz.^{29,34} Moreover, when the size of the molecules increases, many unnecessary excitations can appear in UCCSD which do not improve the chemical accuracy while adding extra-noise due to the extra circuit-depth.³⁵ This reveals the need for more accurate and compact representations of the wavefunction. In that context, various alternative versions of the UCC ansatz, also truncated at the double excitations level have been proposed by the community and have brought interesting upgrades.^{30,36–39} A possible direction also is to use the contracted quantum eigensolvers (CQE) methods which provides an ansatz that can generalize CCSD towards FCI.^{40,41} However, a possible direction towards improving accuracy is to extend the Trotterized UCCSD through adding three-body clusters that represent the (true) Triple T excitations. For example, the gold-standard CCSD(T) method⁴² of (classical) quantum chemistry involves perturbative triple excitations that play a key role in the inclusion of correlation effects.⁴³ The objective of this Letter is to introduce the Trotterized UCCSDT approach and to analyze the behaviour of triple excitations on a set of molecules compared to the initial UCCSD. Of course, an expected downside of the UCCSDT approach is that it involves a large number of parameters to optimize and therefore leads to generate circuits that are excessively long and therefore not suited for their practical use on current NISQ devices. A possible way to cope with this potential inefficiency of UCCSDT (i.e allowing to reduce the required number of parameters) is to use the power of the total spin and point group symmetries. Indeed, taking into account these symmetries enable to use spin factorization and orbital symmetry techniques²³ that have been shown to enable simplifications in the classical coupled cluster equations through eliminating unnecessarily single

and double excitations. Very recently, the point group symmetry constraint has been implemented with the UCCSD ansatz.^{18,26} The authors demonstrated a significant reduction of the number of parameters without affecting the accuracy.

This article is organized as follows: the next section is devoted to a description of the theory of Unitary Coupled Cluster method for electronic structure calculations. It includes the detailed formalism of triple excitations. It is given in its simplified form after application of both spin and orbital symmetries. The subsequent section presents the computational materials used to describe the UCCSDT-VQE approach and the last section illustrates the application of UCCSDT-VQE by showing numerical results through testing several molecules. Comparisons were made with UCCSD as well as the classical methods such as CCSD, CCSD(T), CCSDT-full and FCI.

Theory

In this work we have based ourselves on the Born-Oppenheimer clamped-nuclei Hamiltonian formalism:

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{p,q} h_{pq} \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_q + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{p,q,r,s} h_{pqrs} \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_q^\dagger \hat{a}_r \hat{a}_s \quad (1)$$

where a_p^\dagger (a_q) are anti-commuting operators that create (annihilate) electrons in molecular spin-orbital p (q), respectively. The symbols h_{pq} and h_{pqrs} denote the one- and two-body integrals of the corresponding operators and spin-orbitals in Dirac notation, respectively. These integrals can be easily computed on a classical computer.

The main goal is to find the ground state energy E_0 of Hamiltonian \hat{H} given in eq. (1). The Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE), a hybrid quantum classical algorithm was designed to solve this problem (see Figure 1 in⁹). The principal of VQE is that the quantum computer prepares and measures, for any given parameter $\vec{\theta}$, the parametrized quantum state $|\Psi(\vec{\theta})\rangle$ while the classical computer is used for optimization to propose and update $\vec{\theta}$, in order to minimize the variational energy $\langle \Psi(\vec{\theta}) | H | \Psi(\vec{\theta}) \rangle \geq E_0$.

We focus on the Unitary Coupled Cluster (UCC) wavefunction, which, as mentioned in the intro-

duction, is chemically inspired from the classical Coupled Cluster (CC) method, that has yielded high-accuracy results in classical quantum chemistry. The UCC theory is important in our study, since its wavefunction is unitary and therefore can be efficiently implemented on the quantum computer unlike the regular CC method. The UCC wavefunction can be expressed as follows:

$$|\Psi(\vec{\theta})\rangle = e^{\hat{T}(\vec{\theta}) - \hat{T}^\dagger(\vec{\theta})} |\psi_{\text{HF}}\rangle \quad (2)$$

where \hat{T} is the so-called cluster excitation operator and \hat{T}^\dagger is its Hermitian conjugate. $|\psi_{\text{HF}}\rangle$ is the reference Hartree-Fock state. Since we are interested in investigating the effect of Triple excitations on UCC's accuracy, the coupled-cluster excitations $\hat{T}(\vec{\theta})$ are truncated to single, double and triple excitations to introduce UCCSDT,

$$\hat{T}(\vec{\theta}) = \hat{T}_1(\vec{\theta}) + \hat{T}_2(\vec{\theta}) + \hat{T}_3(\vec{\theta}) = \sum_{a,i} \theta_i^a \hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_i + \sum_{a,b,i,j} \theta_{i,j}^{a,b} \hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_b^\dagger \hat{a}_i \hat{a}_j + \sum_{a,b,c,i,j,k} \theta_{i,j,k}^{a,b,c} \hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_b^\dagger \hat{a}_c^\dagger \hat{a}_i \hat{a}_j \hat{a}_k \quad (3)$$

where $a, b, c \in \text{virt}$, $i, j, k \in \text{occ}$, θ_i^a , $\theta_{i,j}^{a,b}$ and $\theta_{i,j,k}^{a,b,c}$ are the variational parameters. The triple excitation term $\hat{T}_3(\vec{\theta})$ (given in equation (3)) increases drastically the number of parameters as n_o increases. This makes the optimization process very difficult and slow to reach convergence. However, as discussed in the introduction, the many excitations appearing in the UCCSDT wavefunction (single, double and triple) are not all important and will not affect all the correlation energy. Therefore, determining, *a priori*, those unimportant amplitudes, and thus not including them in equation (3) above before compilation and execution of a variational optimization of the parameters, is highly significant to save resources. In this work we focus only on neutral closed-shell molecular species allow to make the electronic calculations on such molecules very efficient by exploiting simultaneously both spin and orbital symmetries in the UCCSDT ansatz. Indeed, since in the neutral closed-shell molecules exhibit an even number of electrons, one can maintain only excitations that can satisfy spin symmetry through keeping the balance between spin-up(\uparrow) and spin-down(\downarrow) electrons. Therefore it is straightforward to include the spin symmetry constraint in equation (3). The inclusion of orbital symmetry constraints requires more precise explanation for

its implementation for each molecule subject to a non-trivial point group symmetry.^{44,45} For example the H₂ and N₂ molecules belongs to the $D_{\infty h}$ point group whereas LiH and H₂O belong to $C_{\infty v}$. Each such group is characterized by its irreducible representations (irreps) which are listed in.⁴⁶ Let us now describe how to impose the orbital symmetry constraint from each irreps group into equation (3) following the rules that are given in chapter 2 of reference,²³ and that were recently reviewed in.²⁶ First, we use the orbital symmetry operator \hat{s}_e , noted in,²⁶ which maps

- each orbital to the irreps of that orbital
- each pair of orbitals to the tensor product of the two irreps of the two orbitals
- each triple of orbitals to the tensor product of the three irreps of the three orbitals

Assuming e.g. that the D_{2h} group is used, and taking for example the triple excitation case, if the irreps of i, j, k are $i = A_u, j = B_{1g}, k = B_{2u}$, then we have : $\hat{s}_e(i) = A_u, \hat{s}_e(j) = B_{1g}, \hat{s}_e(k) = B_{2u}$ and $\hat{s}_e(i, j, k) = B_{3g}$ according to the multiplication table for D_{2h} . Then, the complexity reduction comes from the rule that single excitations must only occur between orbitals that belong to the same irreps. Double and Triple excitations must only occur between occupied and virtual orbitals whose tensor product irreps are similar. Furthermore, the products of irreps that are partaken in each excitation must contain the fully symmetric irreps.

Merging these constraints with the spin symmetry, we obtain the operator for Singles (S)

$$\hat{T}_1(\vec{\theta}) - \hat{T}_1^\dagger(\vec{\theta}) = \sum_{\substack{i, a \in \{\uparrow\} \\ \hat{s}_e(i) = \hat{s}_e(a)}} \theta_i^a (\hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_i - \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_a) + \sum_{\substack{\bar{i}, \bar{a} \in \{\downarrow\} \\ \hat{s}_e(\bar{i}) = \hat{s}_e(\bar{a})}} \theta_{\bar{i}}^{\bar{a}} (\hat{a}_{\bar{a}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{i}} - \hat{a}_{\bar{i}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{a}}) \quad (4)$$

For Doubles (D),

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}_2(\vec{\theta}) - \hat{T}_2^\dagger(\vec{\theta}) = & \sum_{\substack{i < j, a < b \in \{\uparrow\} \\ \hat{s}_e(i, j) = \hat{s}_e(a, b)}} \theta_{i, j}^{a, b} (\hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_b^\dagger \hat{a}_j \hat{a}_i - \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_j^\dagger \hat{a}_b \hat{a}_a) + \sum_{\substack{\bar{i} < \bar{j}, \bar{a} < \bar{b} \in \{\downarrow\} \\ \hat{s}_e(\bar{i}, \bar{j}) = \hat{s}_e(\bar{a}, \bar{b})}} \theta_{\bar{i}, \bar{j}}^{\bar{a}, \bar{b}} (\hat{a}_{\bar{a}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{b}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{j}} \hat{a}_{\bar{i}} - \hat{a}_{\bar{i}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{j}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{b}} \hat{a}_{\bar{a}}) \\ & + \sum_{\substack{i, \bar{j}, a, \bar{b} \\ i, a \in \{\uparrow\}; \bar{j}, \bar{b} \in \{\downarrow\} \\ \hat{s}_e(i, \bar{j}) = \hat{s}_e(a, \bar{b})}} \theta_{i, \bar{j}}^{a, \bar{b}} (\hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{b}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{j}} \hat{a}_i - \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{j}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{b}} \hat{a}_a) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

For Triples (T),

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{T}_3(\vec{\theta}) - \hat{T}_3^\dagger(\vec{\theta}) = & \sum_{\substack{i < j < k \in \{\uparrow\} \\ a < b < c \in \{\uparrow\} \\ \hat{s}_e(i, j, k) = \hat{s}_e(a, b, c)}} \theta_{i, j, k}^{a, b, c} (\hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_b^\dagger \hat{a}_c^\dagger \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_j \hat{a}_i - \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_j^\dagger \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_c \hat{a}_b \hat{a}_a) + \sum_{\substack{\bar{i} < \bar{j} < \bar{k} \in \{\downarrow\} \\ \bar{a} < \bar{b} < \bar{c} \in \{\downarrow\} \\ \hat{s}_e(\bar{i}, \bar{j}, \bar{k}) = \hat{s}_e(\bar{a}, \bar{b}, \bar{c})}} \theta_{\bar{i}, \bar{j}, \bar{k}}^{\bar{a}, \bar{b}, \bar{c}} (\hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_b^\dagger \hat{a}_c^\dagger \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_j \hat{a}_i - \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_j^\dagger \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_c \hat{a}_b \hat{a}_a) \\
& + \sum_{\substack{i < j, a < b \in \{\uparrow\} \\ \bar{k}, \bar{c} \in \{\downarrow\} \\ \hat{s}_e(i, j, \bar{k}) = \hat{s}_e(a, b, \bar{c})}} \theta_{i, j, \bar{k}}^{a, b, \bar{c}} (\hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_b^\dagger \hat{a}_c^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{k}} \hat{a}_j \hat{a}_i - \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_j^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{k}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\bar{c}} \hat{a}_b \hat{a}_a) + \sum_{\substack{\bar{i} < \bar{j}, \bar{a} < \bar{b} \in \{\downarrow\} \\ k, c \in \{\uparrow\} \\ \hat{s}_e(i, j, \bar{k}) = \hat{s}_e(a, b, \bar{c})}} \theta_{\bar{i}, \bar{j}, k}^{\bar{a}, \bar{b}, c} (\hat{a}_a^\dagger \hat{a}_b^\dagger \hat{a}_c^\dagger \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_j \hat{a}_i - \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_j^\dagger \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_c \hat{a}_b \hat{a}_a)
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

With these excitations we construct the symmetric UCCSDT, which is named throughout the text as sym-UCCSDT.

Computational Procedure

The implementation of an exponential operator $e^{\hat{T}(\vec{\theta}) - \hat{T}^\dagger(\vec{\theta})}$ given in eq. (2) cannot be done directly on quantum hardware. Therefore applying Trotterization using the Suzuki–Trotter expansion²⁷ is mandatory to break up the exponential of a sum as a product of individual exponentials. Thus we used this approach to write the Trotterized $e^{\hat{T}(\vec{\theta}) - \hat{T}^\dagger(\vec{\theta})}$ with $T(\theta) - T(\theta)^\dagger$ (eq. (3)) in the form:

$$e^{\hat{T}(\vec{\theta}) - \hat{T}^\dagger(\vec{\theta})} = \left(\prod_{\rho} e^{\frac{\theta_{\rho}}{t} (T_{\rho} - T_{\rho}^\dagger)} \right)^t + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{t}\right) \tag{7}$$

where t is the number of Trotter steps and ρ corresponds to the elements of excitations introduced in equation (3). The essential tools needed to perform the VQE process (such as fermionic second quantization of \hat{H} equation (1), fermion-qubit transforms using Jordan-Wigner representation,⁴⁷ Trotterization, etc) are implemented in the myQLM-fermion package.^{48,49} We use the UCC family module from our OpenVQE package^{49,50} to implement UCCSDT excitations (equations (4) – (6)). We also used PySCF package⁵¹ to evaluate the molecular orbital integrals h_{pq} and h_{pqrs} which are given in equation (1). Using PySCF package, we determine automatically the irreps of each molecular orbital as well as the direct tensor product of the irrep of the molecular spin-orbitals

by using the product table.⁴⁶ Finally, we used a gradient-based optimization method (BFGS) from *scipy.optimize* library⁵² for optimizing the variational parameters θ_i^a , $\theta_{i,j}^{a,b}$ and $\theta_{i,j,k}^{a,b,c}$. The gradient norm used is equal to 10^{-10} .

For the calculation of classical chemistry methods CCSD and CCSD(T), we use PYSCF package. However for the full CCSDT, we use CCT3⁵³ plugin that is provided in Psi4 package.⁵⁴ Given that CC(t;3) method is supposed to yield practically as accurate as full CCSDT for total electronic energies. The energy convergence threshold used is 10^{-10} Ha.

Numerical Results and Discussions

We tested our UCCSDT-VQE (eq. (3)) and sym-UCCSDT-VQE (eqs. (4) – (6)) methods on three sets of molecules: LiH, BeH₂ and H₂O. For sym-UCCSD and sym-UCCSDT-VQE calculations, we chose the highest possible Abelian point groups that belong to each of the systems i.e by referring to⁵⁵ we have C_{2v} point group for LiH and H₂O but D_{2h} point group for BeH₂. The minimal STO-3G basis⁵⁶ is used in order to minimize the computational costs. Within the STO-3G basis set, LiH has a Hilbert space spanned by 12 Hartree-Fock (HF) orbitals (4 occupied, 8 virtual). BeH₂ has 14 HF orbitals (6 occupied, 8 virtual), H₂O has 14 HF orbitals (10 occupied, 4 virtual). In the multi-qubit register, we assign each qubit to a spin-orbital, thus LiH (BeH₂ and H₂O) is (are) represented by 12 (14) qubits. We used the Quantum Learning Machine⁴⁹ (QLM) simulator that is able to simulate up to 40 qubits (with large memory), and we used the noiseless simulation mode (i.e. such ideal simulator mimics the behavior of performing the experiment with an infinite number of shots) in order to minimize computational run time and memory demands. First, we tested the two methods on the LiH molecule at two bond lengths: $R = 1.0 \text{ \AA}$ and $R = 3.0 \text{ \AA}$. As shown in Table 1, we observe that UCCSD and sym-UCCSD brings similar numerical results. A similar observation can be made for the UCCSDT and sym-UCCSDT results. This demonstrates that the presence of spin and orbital symmetries in sym-UCC-VQE reaches the same result as UCC-VQE but in a more efficient way and without influencing the overall accuracy. For example, Table 2

shows that the number of parameters is reduced from 188 to 58 for the case of LiH, which in practice accelerates the optimization due to the fact that a lower dimensional optimization problem is tackled. We confirm the convergence of sym-UCCSD and sym-UCCSDT energies at gradient norm equal to 10^{-10} inside BFGS optimizer (see the convergence as a function of optimization steps in Figure 1 of the Supplementary Materials⁵⁷).

Table 1: UCC-VQE simulations for LiH at various bond lengths: $R = 1.0 \text{ \AA}$ and $R = 3.0 \text{ \AA}$. The obtained UCC-energies are in Hartree (Ha). The error (Err) is the difference between the estimated UCC-energy and the FCI (the reference result is given in the last row).

Method	R=1.0 Å		R=3.0 Å	
	Ener. (Ha)	Err. (Ha)	Ener. (Ha)	Err. (Ha)
UCCSD	-7.78445508682	5.19×10^{-6}	-7.7987523587	9.08×10^{-5}
Sym.UCCSD	-7.78445509065	5.18×10^{-6}	-7.79875240726	9.07×10^{-5}
UCCSDT(this work)	-7.78446025863	2.14×10^{-8}	-7.79884308319	7.63×10^{-8}
Sym.UCCSDT	-7.78446025863	2.13×10^{-8}	-7.79884308642	7.30×10^{-8}
FCI (STO-3G)	-7.78446028003		-7.79884315950	

As mentioned in the literature,^{25,26,30,49,58} testing the Trotterization effect in the UCC ansatz is important since, as seen in equation (7), using $t > 1$ might in principle, decrease the Trotterization error. Besides Trotterization study, a different method called disentangled UCC ansatz⁵⁹ has been introduced, and in⁶⁰ the ordering of operators in this ansatz has been discussed. In our case we are interested in focusing on Trotterized ansatz truncated at Triple excitations. To test this in our symmetric operators, we use the sym-UCCSD and sym-UCCSDT methods with different Trotter steps t . It should be noted that when we increased it beyond 1, the same ansatz (and associated parameters) was chosen first and then we extended it. We observe in Table 2 of the Supplementary Materials⁵⁷ that increasing t , from $t = 1$ up to $t = 15$ steps does not impact the results. A similar conclusion is observed in the sym-UCCSDT case when we increased t from $t = 1$ up to $t = 3$ steps. We have thus carefully checked that most of the operators that are involved in the symmetric version actually do not commute (see Table 3, Supplementary Materials⁵⁷) so that – a priori – there should be, at least, a slight difference in the optimized discrete energies with different values

of t , but also there should be a difference on the coefficients in front of the operators (results not shown : the coefficients for t are those obtained for $t = 1$ divided by t). The reason we found is that – a posteriori, i.e. after computation – we verified that, in both cases the operators associated to non-negligible coefficients do commute (i.e. the coefficients in front of non commuting operators are negligible). We do not see reasons for this but it needs to be further analyzed.

In the remaining part of this Letter, we therefore use a UCC ansatz truncated at the Single, Double, and Triple excitations using a single Trotter step.

When applying the point group symmetry method, the number of optimization parameters was reduced between 14.2% (case of BeH_2 having a D_{2h} point group symmetry) and 30.8% (case of LiH having a C_{2v} point group symmetry), as shown in Table 2. This consequently will significantly reduce the gate cost of implementing triple excitations on quantum computers. Despite this reduction in parameters in the sym-UCCSDT circuit-ansatz, this circuit depth can be still considered as high compared to current NISQ devices capabilities. This is linked to the fact that we are using the CNOT staircase^{4,61} method that maps the exponential of each fermionic excitation into one- and two-qubit gates. Therefore, the number of CNOT (2-qubit gate) increases with the level of excitations: 12 for single, 48 for double and 320 for Triples. Then the circuit depths are 21, 84, 464, respectively. This can be illustrated for example with the BeH_2 case, as shown in Table 2. It contains 92 parameters, associated to the following excitations: 8 singles, 26 doubles, 52 triples, leading to a total CNOT gates in Sym-UCCSDT circuit equal to $12 \times 8 + 48 \times 26 + 320 \times 52 = 17984$. Attempts for reducing the CNOT counts in triple excitation operators and higher-orders have been recently proposed.⁶² However, even with this reduction in CNOT counts, UCCSDT ansatz are not yet amendable to current NISQ devices. Now let us discuss about sym-UCCSD and sym-UCCSDT energy errors, one of the main focus in the article. It is important to note that we will not consider the ordering of operators in the ansatz since it is believed to bring only little accuracy improvements.³⁰ However, it will, of course, remain of potential interest to further study its impact. We believe that the inclusion of triple excitations should generate a sufficient improvement of the ansatz quality. The energy error we study is the difference between

Table 2: UCC-VQE simulations for LiH, H₂O and BeH₂ calculated at equilibrium. The geometry data are taken from CCCBDB-NIST Database.⁵⁵ Columns 2 and 3 corresponds to the number of qubits and to the point group used in each of the molecules, respectively. The original parameters (and the parameters after reduction) are given in the 4th column and the percent of the operators used (i.e single, double and triple excitations) after parameters reduction are in column 5. The UCC-VQE energy differences compared with the FCI energy (Ha) are shown from the 6th to 8th columns. Data of $\Delta E_{SymUCCSD}$ are taken from ref.¹⁸ Symbol(*) represents this work.

	Qbits	Sym.	Para Bef.(Af.)	%	$\Delta E_{SymUCCSD}$ ¹⁸	$\Delta E_{SymUCCSD}^*$	$\Delta E_{SymUCCSDT}^*$
LiH	12	C _{2v}	188 (58)	30.8%	1.09×10^{-5}	1.06×10^{-5}	2.16×10^{-8}
H ₂ O	14	C _{2v}	340 (104)	30.5%	1.09×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-4}	2.11×10^{-6}
BeH ₂	14	D _{2h}	644 (92)	14.2%	3.82×10^{-4}	3.81×10^{-4}	6.63×10^{-6}

the predicted UCC energy and FCI energy at the STO-3G basis set level. When the molecules are chosen at their equilibrium geometry (see Table 2), the obtained sym-UCCSD error is similar to the one obtained in reference,¹⁸ with only a very small difference of $\approx 10^{-7}$ Ha. The calculated sym-UCCSDT improves the accuracy with respect to sym-UCCSD by about 3 orders of magnitude in LiH and by about 2-order of magnitudes in H₂O and BeH₂ molecules. This illustrates the capabilities of Triple excitations to recover the correlation energy missed by the sym-UCCSD ansatz at equilibrium. Moreover we calculate the sym-UCCSD and sym-UCCSDT energies for LiH and BeH₂ at several bond lengths R ranging between 0.5 Å to 3.5 Å, see Figure 1. As shown in the Figure, in the LiH case, the sym-UCCSD and sym-UCCSDT errors remain below the chemical accuracy for all bond lengths and the difference between sym-UCCSDT and sym-UCCSD error is again about 3 orders of magnitude smaller. In the BeH₂ case, when R is 2.0 Å, sym-UCCSD error starts to get above the chemical accuracy (1.6×10^{-3} Hartree) and it gets further away as R increases. Overall, in term of error, Sym-UCCSDT is better than sym-UCCSD ones by about 1-2 order of magnitudes at all bond lengths. It remains below the chemical accuracy, except when R is 2.5 Å and beyond, where the error starts to approach the blue line delimiting the chemical accuracy. When R is equal to 2.75 Å, a discontinuity is observed. In fact this has been also seen in a previous work, see reference,⁶³ around this bond length in BeH₂ calculated at STO-3G basis set

level. There is one hypothesis which illustrates this anomaly. Indeed, the importance of dynamic correlation starts to increase when the bond length is around 2.7\AA . At this point, according to figure 5 in⁶³ the occupation number of the natural orbitals starts to differ from zero or two. Hence many natural orbitals would have significant occupation numbers (i.e different from zero), so the difference between occupied and virtual orbitals tend to disappear. This probably leads to the inability of our sym-UCCSDT approach to capture some important excitations that might contribute strongly to the dynamical correlation, and thus the sym-UCCSDT errors could increase. In general, this limitation from triple excitations at large bond lengths in BeH_2 can be probably improved by adding higher-order excitations but is consistent with classical couple cluster behaviours and the limits of single determinant approaches. The data which were used to plot Figure 1 are provided in Tables 4 and 5 from the Supplementary Informations.⁵⁷ In order to compare the classical methods

Figure 1: Error of the UCCSD and UCCSDT simulations using both spin and point group symmetries for geometries LiH and BeH_2 at different bond lengths. The horizontal blue line represents the chemical accuracy, i.e. 1.6×10^{-3} Ha.

with UCC-VQE simulations, we calculated CCSD, CCSD(T) and CCSDT-full errors for LiH, H_2O and BeH_2 at equilibrium. The results are shown in Table 3. CCSD and sym-UCCSD errors are very similar. This is also observed in³⁴ where Orbital optimized (OO)-UCCSD method has been tested. The CCSD(T) errors deviates clearly from sym-UCCSDT errors by at least one order of magnitudes. sym-UCCSDT also surpasses CCSDT-full(i.e Coupled cluster with a full treatment

of singles, doubles and triples) in the three molecules, which is the most remarkable outcome here (see also same behavior in Figures 2 (a) and 2(b) of the supplementary materials⁵⁷ at some bond lengths in LiH and BeH₂, respectively). Such behaviour has been noticed in,³⁷ where it is always CCSDT that has lower quality than UCCSDT, which was calculated analytically.

Table 3: Error comparison between Classical methods (CCSD, CCSD(T) and CCSDT-full) and UCC-VQE (sym.UCCSD and sym.UCCSDT) simulations for LiH, H₂O and BeH₂ calculated at equilibrium. The geometry data are taken from CCCBDB-NIST Database. The UCC-VQE results are referred from Table 2, and those of CCSD, CCSD(T), CCSDT-full are from Table 5 of the Supplementary Material.⁵⁷ The last column represents the FCI energies at STO-3G basis set. The error is the difference between the obtained energy and FCI in (Ha).

	ΔE_{CCSD}	$\Delta E_{SymUCCSD}^*$	$\Delta E_{CCSD(T)}$	$\Delta E_{CCSDT-full}$	$\Delta E_{SymUCCSDT}^*$	FCI
LiH	1.05×10^{-5}	1.06×10^{-5}	2.11×10^{-6}	2.79×10^{-8}	2.16×10^{-8}	-7.882403410335502
H ₂ O	1.17×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-4}	4.91×10^{-5}	2.17×10^{-5}	2.11×10^{-6}	-75.01257824109094
BeH ₂	3.94×10^{-4}	3.81×10^{-4}	1.84×10^{-4}	4.22×10^{-5}	6.63×10^{-6}	-15.595176868923053

Conclusion

In conclusion, in this article, we presented the Trotterized UCCSDT ansatz. We simplified the unitary coupled cluster triple excitation equations by using the spin and point group symmetries. By testing several molecules on QLM simulator, we demonstrated that the efficiency of the symmetric UCCSDT method can greatly improved. Indeed, reducing the non-important single, double and triple excitations from the circuit ansatz, one can accelerate the convergence process as well as reducing the circuit depth. Moreover, by performing several numerical simulations, we showed that the symmetric UCCSDT is able to reach a superior accuracy compared to UCCSD (by at least two orders of magnitudes). In the future, as quantum simulators and Quantum Processing Units improve and enable to handle more gates, the Trotterized UCCSDT should enable to perform accurate calculations with large chemical basis sets (i.e beyond the minimal STO-3G). Overall, the Trotterized UCCSDT can bring interesting results for the general quantum chemistry community

since it is shown to be competitive with "gold-standard" CCSD(T) classical methods.

Acknowledgement

M.R. acknowledges funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, more specifically the $\langle \text{NE}|\text{AS}|\text{QC} \rangle$ project under grant agreement No. 951821. This work has also received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant agreement No 810367), project EMC2 (JPP, YM). Support from the PEPR EPiQ and HQI programs is acknowledged.

Supporting Information Available

In the Supplementary Materials,⁵⁷ we present all data related to the computed total energies for sym-UCCSD and sym-UCCSDT found in Tables 1, 2 and 3. Additionally, a detailed sketch algorithm that describe the triple excitations within spin and point group symmetries is presented and coded in our openVQE package.⁵⁰

References

- (1) Aspuru-Guzik, A.; Dutoi, A. D.; Love, P. J.; Head-Gordon, M. Simulated quantum computation of molecular energies. *Science* **2005**, *309*, 1704–1707.
- (2) Reiher, M.; Wiebe, N.; Svore, K. M.; Wecker, D.; Troyer, M. Elucidating reaction mechanisms on quantum computers. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences* **2017**, *114*, 7555–7560.
- (3) Bauer, B.; Bravyi, S.; Motta, M.; Chan, G. K.-L. Quantum algorithms for quantum chemistry and quantum materials science. *Chemical Reviews* **2020**, *120*, 12685–12717.

- (4) McArdle, S.; Endo, S.; Aspuru-Guzik, A.; Benjamin, S. C.; Yuan, X. Quantum computational chemistry. *Reviews of Modern Physics* **2020**, *92*, 015003.
- (5) Bassman, L.; Urbanek, M.; Metcalf, M.; Carter, J.; Kemper, A. F.; de Jong, W. A. Simulating quantum materials with digital quantum computers. *Quantum Science and Technology* **2021**, *6*, 043002.
- (6) Gan, Z.; Grant, D. J.; Harrison, R. J.; Dixon, D. A. The lowest energy states of the group-III A–group-V A heteronuclear diatomics: BN, BP, AlN, and AlP from full configuration interaction calculations. *The Journal of chemical physics* **2006**, *125*, 124311.
- (7) Lehtola, S.; Tubman, N. M.; Whaley, K. B.; Head-Gordon, M. Cluster decomposition of full configuration interaction wave functions: A tool for chemical interpretation of systems with strong correlation. *The Journal of chemical physics* **2017**, *147*, 154105.
- (8) Vogiatzis, K. D.; Ma, D.; Olsen, J.; Gagliardi, L.; De Jong, W. A. Pushing configuration-interaction to the limit: Towards massively parallel MCSCF calculations. *The Journal of chemical physics* **2017**, *147*, 184111.
- (9) Peruzzo, A.; McClean, J.; Shadbolt, P.; Yung, M.-H.; Zhou, X.-Q.; Love, P. J.; Aspuru-Guzik, A.; O’Brien, J. L. A variational eigenvalue solver on a photonic quantum processor. *Nature communications* **2014**, *5*, 1–7.
- (10) McClean, J. R.; Romero, J.; Babbush, R.; Aspuru-Guzik, A. The theory of variational hybrid quantum-classical algorithms. *New Journal of Physics* **2016**, *18*, 023023.
- (11) Cerezo, M.; Arrasmith, A.; Babbush, R.; Benjamin, S. C.; Endo, S.; Fujii, K.; McClean, J. R.; Mitarai, K.; Yuan, X.; Cincio, L., et al. Variational quantum algorithms. *Nature Reviews Physics* **2021**, *3*, 625–644.
- (12) Li, W.; Huang, Z.; Cao, C.; Huang, Y.; Shuai, Z.; Sun, X.; Sun, J.; Yuan, X.; Lv, D. Toward

- practical quantum embedding simulation of realistic chemical systems on near-term quantum computers. *Chemical science* **2022**, *13*, 8953–8962.
- (13) O'Malley, P. J.; Babbush, R.; Kivlichan, I. D.; Romero, J.; McClean, J. R.; Barends, R.; Kelly, J.; Roushan, P.; Tranter, A.; Ding, N., et al. Scalable quantum simulation of molecular energies. *Physical Review X* **2016**, *6*, 031007.
- (14) Bharti, K.; Cervera-Lierta, A.; Kyaw, T. H.; Haug, T.; Alperin-Lea, S.; Anand, A.; Degroote, M.; Heimonen, H.; Kottmann, J. S.; Menke, T., et al. Noisy intermediate-scale quantum algorithms. *Reviews of Modern Physics* **2022**, *94*, 015004.
- (15) Kühn, M.; Zanker, S.; Deglmann, P.; Marthaler, M.; Weiß, H. Accuracy and resource estimations for quantum chemistry on a near-term quantum computer. *Journal of chemical theory and computation* **2019**, *15*, 4764–4780.
- (16) Lolur, P.; Rahm, M.; Skogh, M.; García-Álvarez, L.; Wendin, G. Benchmarking the variational quantum eigensolver through simulation of the ground state energy of prebiotic molecules on high-performance computers. *AIP Conference Proceedings*. 2021; p 030005.
- (17) Yeter-Aydeniz, K.; Gard, B. T.; Jakowski, J.; Majumder, S.; Barron, G. S.; Siopsis, G.; Humble, T. S.; Pooser, R. C. Benchmarking quantum chemistry computations with variational, imaginary time evolution, and Krylov space solver algorithms. *Advanced Quantum Technologies* **2021**, *4*, 2100012.
- (18) Cao, C.; Hu, J.; Zhang, W.; Xu, X.; Chen, D.; Yu, F.; Li, J.; Hu, H.-S.; Lv, D.; Yung, M.-H. Progress toward larger molecular simulation on a quantum computer: Simulating a system with up to 28 qubits accelerated by point-group symmetry. *Phys. Rev. A* **2022**, *105*, 062452.
- (19) Quantum, G. A.; Collaborators*†,; Arute, F.; Arya, K.; Babbush, R.; Bacon, D.; Bardin, J. C.; Barends, R.; Boixo, S.; Broughton, M.; Buckley, B. B., et al. Hartree-Fock on a superconducting qubit quantum computer. *Science* **2020**, *369*, 1084–1089.

- (20) Kandala, A.; Mezzacapo, A.; Temme, K.; Takita, M.; Brink, M.; Chow, J. M.; Gambetta, J. M. Hardware-efficient variational quantum eigensolver for small molecules and quantum magnets. *Nature* **2017**, *549*, 242–246.
- (21) Hempel, C.; Maier, C.; Romero, J.; McClean, J.; Monz, T.; Shen, H.; Jurcevic, P.; Lanyon, B. P.; Love, P.; Babbush, R., et al. Quantum chemistry calculations on a trapped-ion quantum simulator. *Physical Review X* **2018**, *8*, 031022.
- (22) Tazhigulov, R. N.; Sun, S.-N.; Haghshenas, R.; Zhai, H.; Tan, A. T.; Rubin, N. C.; Babbush, R.; Minnich, A. J.; Chan, G. K.-L. Simulating Models of Challenging Correlated Molecules and Materials on the Sycamore Quantum Processor. *PRX Quantum* **2022**, *3*, 040318.
- (23) Crawford, T. D.; Schaefer III, H. F. An introduction to coupled cluster theory for computational chemists. *Reviews in computational chemistry* **2007**, *14*, 33–136.
- (24) Bartlett, R. J.; Musiał, M. Coupled-cluster theory in quantum chemistry. *Reviews of Modern Physics* **2007**, *79*, 291.
- (25) Romero, J.; Babbush, R.; McClean, J. R.; Hempel, C.; Love, P. J.; Aspuru-Guzik, A. Strategies for quantum computing molecular energies using the unitary coupled cluster ansatz. *Quantum Science and Technology* **2018**, *4*, 014008.
- (26) Anand, A.; Schleich, P.; Alperin-Lea, S.; Jensen, P. W.; Sim, S.; Díaz-Tinoco, M.; Kottmann, J. S.; Degroote, M.; Izmaylov, A. F.; Aspuru-Guzik, A. A quantum computing view on unitary coupled cluster theory. *Chemical Society Reviews* **2022**,
- (27) Hatano, N.; Suzuki, M. *Quantum annealing and other optimization methods*; Springer, 2005; pp 37–68.
- (28) Sokolov, I. O.; Barkoutsos, P. K.; Ollitrault, P. J.; Greenberg, D.; Rice, J.; Pistoia, M.; Tavernelli, I. Quantum orbital-optimized unitary coupled cluster methods in the strongly corre-

- lated regime: Can quantum algorithms outperform their classical equivalents? *The Journal of chemical physics* **2020**, *152*, 124107.
- (29) Xia, R.; Kais, S. Qubit coupled cluster singles and doubles variational quantum eigensolver ansatz for electronic structure calculations. *Quantum Science and Technology* **2020**, *6*, 015001.
- (30) Grimsley, H. R.; Claudino, D.; Economou, S. E.; Barnes, E.; Mayhall, N. J. Is the trotterized uccsd ansatz chemically well-defined? *Journal of chemical theory and computation* **2019**, *16*, 1–6.
- (31) Yung, M.-H.; Casanova, J.; Mezzacapo, A.; McClean, J.; Lamata, L.; Aspuru-Guzik, A.; Solano, E. From transistor to trapped-ion computers for quantum chemistry. *Scientific reports* **2014**, *4*, 1–7.
- (32) Shen, Y.; Zhang, X.; Zhang, S.; Zhang, J.-N.; Yung, M.-H.; Kim, K. Quantum implementation of the unitary coupled cluster for simulating molecular electronic structure. *Physical Review A* **2017**, *95*, 020501.
- (33) O’Brien, T. E.; Anselmetti, G.; Gkritis, F.; Elfving, V.; Polla, S.; Huggins, W. J.; Oumarou, O.; Kechedzhi, K.; Abanin, D.; Acharya, R., et al. Purification-based quantum error mitigation of pair-correlated electron simulations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.10799* **2022**,
- (34) Mizukami, W.; Mitarai, K.; Nakagawa, Y. O.; Yamamoto, T.; Yan, T.; Ohnishi, Y.-y. Orbital optimized unitary coupled cluster theory for quantum computer. *Physical Review Research* **2020**, *2*, 033421.
- (35) Sennane, W.; Piquemal, J.-P.; Rančić, M. J. Calculating the ground-state energy of benzene under spatial deformations with noisy quantum computing. *Phys. Rev. A* **2023**, *107*, 012416.
- (36) Lee, J.; Huggins, W. J.; Head-Gordon, M.; Whaley, K. B. Generalized unitary coupled cluster

- wave functions for quantum computation. *Journal of chemical theory and computation* **2018**, *15*, 311–324.
- (37) Köhn, A.; Olsen, J. Capabilities and limits of the unitary coupled-cluster approach with generalized two-body cluster operators. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **2022**, *157*, 124110.
- (38) Grimsley, H. R.; Economou, S. E.; Barnes, E.; Mayhall, N. J. An adaptive variational algorithm for exact molecular simulations on a quantum computer. *Nature communications* **2019**, *10*, 1–9.
- (39) Fedorov, D. A.; Alexeev, Y.; Gray, S. K.; Otten, M. Unitary Selective Coupled-Cluster Method. *Quantum* **2022**, *6*, 703.
- (40) Smart, S. E.; Boyn, J.-N.; Mazziotti, D. A. Resolving correlated states of benzyne with an error-mitigated contracted quantum eigensolver. *Physical Review A* **2022**, *105*, 022405.
- (41) Smart, S. E.; Mazziotti, D. A. Quantum solver of contracted eigenvalue equations for scalable molecular simulations on quantum computing devices. *Physical Review Letters* **2021**, *126*, 070504.
- (42) Raghavachari, K. Historical perspective on: A fifth-order perturbation comparison of electron correlation theories [Volume 157, Issue 6, 26 May 1989, Pages 479–483]. *Chem. Phys. Lett* **2013**, *589*, 35–36.
- (43) Ramabhadran, R. O.; Raghavachari, K. Extrapolation to the gold-standard in quantum chemistry: computationally efficient and accurate CCSD (T) energies for large molecules using an automated thermochemical hierarchy. *Journal of chemical theory and computation* **2013**, *9*, 3986–3994.
- (44) Dresselhaus, M. S.; Dresselhaus, G.; Jorio, A. *Group theory: application to the physics of condensed matter*; Springer Science & Business Media, 2007.
- (45) Tinkham, M. *Group Theory and Quantum Mechanics* McGraw-Hill: New York. 1964.

- (46) Atkins, P. W.; Child, M. S.; Phillips, C. S. G. *Tables for group theory*; Oxford University Press Oxford, 1970; Vol. 6.
- (47) Fradkin, E. Jordan-Wigner transformation for quantum-spin systems in two dimensions and fractional statistics. *Physical review letters* **1989**, *63*, 322.
- (48) myqlm-fermion. <https://github.com/myQLM/myqlm-fermion><https://myqlm.github.io/qat-fermion.html>Repository: <https://github.com/myQLM/myqlm-fermion> and documentation: <https://myqlm.github.io/qat-fermion.html>.
- (49) Haidar, M.; Rančić, M. J.; Ayril, T.; Maday, Y.; Piquemal, J.-P. Open Source Variational Quantum Eigensolver Extension of the Quantum Learning Machine (QLM) for Quantum Chemistry. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.08798* **2022**,
- (50) Open-VQE package. <https://github.com/OpenVQE/OpenVQE.git><https://openvqe.github.io/OpenVQE/Repository>: <https://github.com/OpenVQE/OpenVQE.git> and documentation:<https://openvqe.github.io/OpenVQE/>.
- (51) Sun, Q.; Berkelbach, T. C.; Blunt, N. S.; Booth, G. H.; Guo, S.; Li, Z.; Liu, J.; McClain, J. D.; Sayfutyarova, E. R.; Sharma, S., et al. PySCF: the Python-based simulations of chemistry framework. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Molecular Science* **2018**, *8*, e1340.
- (52) Virtanen, P. et al. SciPy 1.0: Fundamental Algorithms for Scientific Computing in Python. *Nature Methods* **2020**, *17*, 261–272.
- (53) CCT3: A PSI4 plugin which performs active-space coupled-cluster CCSDt calculations and which can determine noniterative corrections to CCSDt defining the CC(t;3) approach. https://github.com/piecuch-group/psi4_cct3.
- (54) Smith, D. G.; Burns, L. A.; Simmonett, A. C.; Parrish, R. M.; Schieber, M. C.; Galvelis, R.;

- Kraus, P.; Kruse, H.; Di Remigio, R.; Alenaizan, A., et al. PSI4 1.4: Open-source software for high-throughput quantum chemistry. *The Journal of chemical physics* **2020**, *152*, 184108.
- (55) Johnson, N. R. Computational Chemistry Comparison and Benchmark DataBase. **2022**,
- (56) Hehre, W.; Ditchfield, R.; Stewart, R.; Pople, J. self-consistent molecular orbital methods. iv. use of Gaussian expansions of Slater-type orbitals. Extension to second-row molecules. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **1970**, *52*, 2769–2773.
- (57) Haidar, M.; Rančić, M. J.; Maday, Y.; Piquemal, J.-P. See Supplementary Materials for Triple excitation algorithmic code and the total UCC energies.
- (58) Barkoutsos, P. K.; Gonthier, J. F.; Sokolov, I.; Moll, N.; Salis, G.; Fuhrer, A.; Ganzhorn, M.; Egger, D. J.; Troyer, M.; Mezzacapo, A., et al. Quantum algorithms for electronic structure calculations: Particle-hole Hamiltonian and optimized wave-function expansions. *Physical Review A* **2018**, *98*, 022322.
- (59) Evangelista, F. A.; Chan, G. K.-L.; Scuseria, G. E. Exact parameterization of fermionic wave functions via unitary coupled cluster theory. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **2019**, *151*, 244112.
- (60) Izmaylov, A. F.; Díaz-Tinoco, M.; Lang, R. A. On the order problem in construction of unitary operators for the variational quantum eigensolver. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2020**, *22*, 12980–12986.
- (61) Whitfield, J. D.; Biamonte, J.; Aspuru-Guzik, A. Simulation of electronic structure Hamiltonians using quantum computers. *Molecular Physics* **2011**, *109*, 735–750.
- (62) Magoulas, I.; Evangelista, F. A. CNOT-Efficient Circuits for Arbitrary Rank Many-Body Fermionic and Qubit Excitations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.05771* **2022**,
- (63) Van Raemdonck, M.; Alcoba, D. R.; Poelmans, W.; De Baerdemacker, S.; Torre, A.; Lain, L.; Massaccesi, G. E.; Van Neck, D.; Bultinck, P. Polynomial scaling approximations and dy-

dynamic correlation corrections to doubly occupied configuration interaction wave functions.

The Journal of Chemical Physics **2015**, *143*, 104106.